

ESP Textbook Analysis on Gender Representation

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ABSTRACT :The aims of the study to describe and measure about gender equality representation male and female in a textbook through the monolog texts and pictures in the textbook. The researcher used descriptive quantitative data analysis by elaborating both content or document analysis as a research design. Using the sample of textbook designed for university students of Art program learning English entitled “English for Fine Art Students, this study is conducted by evaluating language items and illustrations dimensions; there are five criteria which are examined in order to find gender equality. There are: 1) the male and female characters, 2) occupational “social roles”, 3) amount of talk, 4) male and female in domestic roles, and 5) firstness based on ten theories of experts. Sample: English textbook containing an array of topics on art. Each of the unit caters in it the skills of reading, speaking and writing. Exercises on vocabulary are also presented in every chapter and are incorporated in reading section. The results show that gender representation in English textbook for Art Program students is inequal in two dimensions. This can be derived from the data about gender representation in terms of language items in monolog texts are 92 male and 33 female as the difference 48% and illustration in pictures are 11 male and 7 female as the difference 22%. In the overall number of the total with percentage of those two criteria dimensions are 103 or 72% for male and 40 or 28% for female.

KEYWORDS – EFL, Gender representation, textbook

I. INTRODUCTION

In society, gender refers to the social characteristics and possibilities associated with being male or female, as well as the social interaction between women and men, as well as girls and boys, all of which are socially created and learnt through process of socialization. Since the term gender is culturally constructed and politically invested, each individual is not a free subject, but rather the object who adopts narration produced by those who have power. As a result, power gap between both sexes may create inequal representation of males and females in many aspects of life. In fact, this gender inequality occurs to various amounts in many nations throughout the world. In 2015, world leaders approved a UN resolution establishing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to work toward a more equal society. The fourth objective is to obtain a high-quality education, while the fifth goal is to achieve gender equality. (Aragonés-González et al., 2020) argues the goals are based on the belief that education may help to reduce inequality in general and gender equality in particular. Despite the fact that the governments of these nations have tried a variety of inventive ways to address the problem, gender inequality still exists in many cultures, particularly in developing countries and the Middle East (Al-Qatawneh & Al Rawashdeh, 2019). In the education system, gender has a significant impact on social life in the school, particularly among students. Some research validates concerns for gender diversity in learning materials, demonstrating how various representations affect different learners' levels of performance (Koster & Litosseliti, 2021). As a result, Indonesia has regulations to promote gender equality in the educational field between males and females. The Indonesian Republic Ministry of Education and Culture No. 81 A Year 2013 policy specifies that educational curriculum is aimed toward the establishment of equitable attitudes and

behaviors with an emphasis on gender equality. Many academics are looking into how male and female characters are depicted in EFL textbooks. Textbooks may and should have a more active part in ensuring diversity than just observing it. (Koster & Litosseliti, 2021) believe that representations have an impact on readers as subjects, and that pictures and messages influence and, to some extent, determine the type of woman, man, or non-binary person we believe we can be. Furthermore, when these concealed messages about gender are conveyed in textbooks, students are more likely to accept them (Al-Qatawneh & Al Rawashdeh, 2019). Textbooks must meet certain criteria in order to be used as teaching materials. According to Adi & Maharani (2018), the proposed criteria include a wide range of issues, including goals and methods, designs and organizational structures, linguistic content, skills and themes, methodology, and supplemental materials such as teacher books and audio recordings. Moreover, some aspects of textbooks must pique students' interest and encourage them to be more active and interactive in the classroom; additionally, all materials must be appropriate for learning the language; and, not only the materials, but also moral values are required to meet high textbook standards.

II. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this study was to define and analyze the representation of males and females in a textbook through the monolog texts and pictures in the textbook. The researcher evaluated language items and illustration dimensions in this study based on theory of ten experts. The checklist instrument is used to gather data on gender representation in EFL textbooks and to analyze gender representation in EFL textbooks.

2.1. Research Sample

An analysis of an English textbook, namely English for Fine Arts for university students of Art programs learning English, was done to determine data sources, data collecting methods, and data collection strategies. The textbook is divided into six sections and has a total of 62 pages, including the cover. From the first to the last sections of the textbook, data was gathered in two ways: as language items in monologue texts and as illustrations in "pictures."

2.2. Research Instrument

The main instrument of this research is a checklist containing the theories of ten experts that can identify aspects of the gender perspective analysed from the language aspects of the textbook. Based on Stockdale (2006), if the difference in the amount obtained from counting the texts and illustrations from stereotypes of women and men is more than 5%, then it is categorized as a gender bias.

Table 1. Language Items

Dimension	Sub-dimension
	<p>The names of male and female characters mentioned in monolog text. The pronouns such as he/his/him/Mr will be categorized in the male group, whereas she/her/Ms/Miss/Mrs. will be categorized in the feminine category.</p> <p>- Stockdale (2006)</p> <p>- Cohen and Manion (1992)</p> <p>- Dominguez, 2003)</p>
<p>Language</p> <p>- (Dominguez, 2003)</p>	<p>Occupational roles relate to the people who work in a certain profession mentioned in monolog text. (e.g. nurse, police, singer, etc.)</p> <p>- Dominguez (2003)</p> <p>- Cohen and Manion (1992)</p> <p>- Porreca (1984)</p>
<p>- (Cohen, L & Manion, 1992)</p> <p>- (Porreca, 1984)</p> <p>- (Stockdale, 2006)</p> <p>- (Hall, 2014)</p>	<p>The term "amount of talk" refers to the male or female individuals who engage in discussion in a dominant manner.</p> <p>- Dominguez (2003)</p> <p>- Hall (2014)</p> <p>- Stockdale (2006)</p>
	<p>In monolog text, male and female domestic roles are discussed, as well as the participants in social events, such as who earns money or does household duties. (For example, a father, a mother, a son, and a daughter)</p> <p>- Cohen and Manion (1992)</p> <p>- Hall (2014)</p>
	<p>Firstness refers to who speaks first in a transactional-interpersonal text, such as she and he or he and she, or mother and father.</p> <p>- Stockdale (2006)</p> <p>- Porreca (1984)</p>

Table 2. Illustrations

Dimension	Sub-dimension
Illustrations	The names of male and female characters appear in the pictures (e.g. he, Mr., she, Ms., Miss, and Mrs.) - Chung (2014) - Sovic and Hus (2014) - Nofal&Qawar (2015)
	Occupational roles relate to the people who work in a certain profession or occupational in the picture (e.g nurse, police, singer, etc.) - (Nofal&Qawar 2015) - (Sovič & Hus, 2015) - (Gharbavi & Mousavi, 2012) - (Gjorup 2006) - (Chung 2014)
	Male and female illustrations “pictures” that do domestic roles (e.g. father, mother, brother and sister) - Gharbavi (2012) - Sovic and Hus (2014) - Nofal&Qawar (2015)

2.3. Analysis Method

Quantitative analysis is a well-developed numerical technique that draws on a wide domain of research (Djamba& Neuman, 2002). The researcher used percentage to calculate male and female in the English book for students of Art program. To get data using percentages, there were three stages. The researcher began by determining the quantity of one gender in each sub-dimension. Then, the researcher discovered both gender's quantity in two dimensions. Finally, the researcher multiplied the percentage by 100 percent. As a result, Stockdale (2006) stated that gender bias is defined as a difference of more than 5% in the numbers obtained by counting male and female stereotype texts and pictures (2006, cited in Emaliana and Tusita 2020).

So, instantly to make a formula to find percentage %

$$\text{sub-dimension of appearances} = \frac{\text{Quantity of (m/f)}}{\text{Quantity of both gender}} \times 100\% =$$

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Language Items

Five sub-dimensions that defined the language item requirements in monolog texts were the names of the male and female characters, a certain profession, amounts of talk refers to the number of male/female partners in a dialogue, male and female in domestic roles, and firstness refers to who emerges first. Based on the fulfillment of any definition in each sub dimension, the gender equity representation in textbook in terms of language items was discovered.

Table 3. Language Items

Sub dimension	Frequency	
	M	F
The names of male and female characters mentioned in monolog text. The pronouns such as he, his, him, Mr. will be categorized in the male group, whereas she, her, Ms. Miss, Mrs. will be categorized in the feminine category.	85	28
Occupational roles relate to the people who work in a certain profession or occupation mentioned in monolog text. (e.g. nurse, police, singer, etc.)	2	1
The term "amount of talk" refers to the male/female individuals who engage in discussion in a dominant manner.	0	0
Male and female domestic roles are discussed, as well as who becomes the actor in social events, such as who earns money or does household duties in monolog text. (For example, a father, a mother, a son, and a daughter)	5	4
Firstness refers to who speaks first in a monolog text, such as she and he or he and she, or mother and father mentioned in transactional-interpersonal text.	0	0
Total	92 74%	33 26%

Most of the monolog texts presented in the textbook uses male characters. As portrayed in the Table 1, (1) monolog texts, there were 85 male and 28 female characters' name identified; (2) there were 2 male and 1 female occupational position; (3) there were 5 males and 4 females in domestic roles. In details, in all units did not have amount of talk between male and female and firstness in monolog text. Based on findings, there was a 48% difference in the adequacy of the textbooks in terms of appear gender equality in language items, with 92 (74%) male and 33 (26%) female. This percentage shows imbalance portion for male and female and indicates as a gender bias.

3.2. Illustrations

The three sub dimensions in term of illustrations in pictures were male and female characters' name, occupational roles, and male and female pictures in domestic roles. Based on the result of any definition in each sub dimension, the gender equality representations in textbooks in terms of illustrations were discovered.

Table 4. Illustrations

Sub dimension	Frequency	
	M	F
The names of male and female characters appear in the pictures (e.g. he, she, Ms., Miss, Mrs., and Mr.)	6	2
Occupational roles relate to the people who work in a certain profession or occupation in the picture (e.g. nurse, police, singer, etc.)	5	5
Male and female illustrations “pictures” that do domestic roles (e.g. father, mother, sister and brother)	0	0
Total (%)	11 61	7 39%

As portrayed in the Table 2, there were 6 for male and 2 for female of characters appear in the pictures and there were 5 for male and 5 for female number of occupational roles appear in the pictures. In detail, in all units did not have male and female pictures that do domestic roles. According to the findings, the textbooks' adequacy in terms of appear gender equality in terms of illustrations was 11 (61%) male and 7 (39%) female with an only 22% difference. This percentage shows the portion for male and female is imbalance based on Stockdale's theory.

Table 5. Overall Number of Gender Representation

Sub dimension	Language Items			Illustration	
	ale	M male	Fe ale	M emale	F
The names of male and female characters	5	8	28	6	2
Occupational roles		2	1	5	5
Amount of talk		0	0	-	-
Male and female domestic roles		5	4	0	0
Firstness		0	0	-	-
	2	9	33	1	7
		Total M		Total Female	
Total number		103		40	
Percentage		72%		28%	

Checklist evaluation is used to scrutinize gender representation in English textbook for university students of Art program. The results were gotten by counting overall of two criteria that consists of 8 sub dimensions in the textbook evaluation checklist. This data showed in table 3 that gender representation in terms of language items in monolog texts were 92 male and 33 female as the difference 48% and illustration in pictures were 11 male and 7 female as the difference 22%. As a result, Stockdale (2006) stated that gender bias is defined as a difference of more than 5%. Especially language dimension showed that male domination than female. In the overall number of the total with percentage of those two criteria dimensions were 103 or 72% for male and 40 or 28% for female. This gender-based social study of the textbook, in general, indicates gender bias as the difference 44% between two dimensions.

The result reflects a widespread belief that men are more important than women in almost every society, implying that they must always come first and have more voice. It can be said, then that this textbook promotes the conventional image of who in society is considered more valuable and essential. This automatic

ranking promotes women's second-class position and is one of the many ways in which men's authority is perpetuated.

IV. CONCLUSION

Gender inequality remain in the educational environment, supporting gendered cultural identities (male and female) through the language used in the classroom and textbooks, as well as the treatment given to boys and girls based on their gender. Based on the finding and discussion of the research and the result the problem of the study, it can be concluded that gender representation in English textbook for Art Program students is unequal. Based on the result, female is underrepresented and marginalized both in written and visual text in English textbook. The textbook's writers may not deliberately subjugate women by illustrating biased representations of men and women, but as members of society who live in "male centered" world, it is not always easy for them to free themselves from the established notion about gender. Finally, gender representation in textbooks should be fair, given that EFL textbooks are among the most significant socialization representations. On the other hand, if gender inequality is not adequately reflected in school textbooks, it will have a detrimental influence on society in the future, resulting in a slew of societal issues.

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